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SPEECH CULTURE AS A COMPONENT OF PROFESSIONAL AND COMMUNICATIVE TRAINING OF FUTURE MEDICAL SPECIALISTS.

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Annotation

The article examines the problem of forming a speech culture among medical students in the context of professionally oriented Russian language teaching. The starting point of the study is the critical position that the traditional model of language training, based primarily on the assimilation of terminology and grammatical structures, is insufficient to prepare the future doctor for real communicative interaction with the patient. The purpose of the work is to substantiate and test a set of modern methods aimed at developing the professional and speech competence of first-year medical students. For three months, an AI simulator of the doctor-patient dialogue, speech simulators with feedback, clinical speech scenarios, genre tasks and elements of the AXIS format were used in the educational process. The results showed that these methods contribute to the development of coherent oral speech, improve the accuracy of medical formulations, develop skills of empathic explanation and a conscious choice of speech strategies. However, the study is of a pilot nature and requires further quantitative verification. The scientific significance of the work consists in considering the culture of speech as an integrative component of the professional training of a future doctor, and not as an auxiliary section of a language course.

Keywords: medical and biological profile, educational and professional communication, medical Russian language, language for special purposes, problems in teaching Russian.

КУЛЬТУРА РЕЧИ КАК КОМПОНЕНТ ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНОЙ И КОММУНИКАТИВНОЙ ПОДГОТОВКИ БУДУЩИХ МЕДИЦИНСКИХ СПЕЦИАЛИСТОВ.

Аннотация

В статье рассматривается проблема формирования культуры речи у студентов медицинских вузов в контексте профессионально ориентированного обучения

русскому языку. Отправной точкой исследования является критическая позиция о том, что традиционная модель языковой подготовки, основанная преимущественно на усвоении терминологии и грамматических структур, недостаточна для подготовки будущего врача к реальному коммуникативному взаимодействию с пациентом. Цель работы — обосновать и апробировать комплекс современных методов, направленных на развитие профессионально-речевой компетенции студентов-медиков первого курса. На протяжении трёх месяцев в учебный процесс были включены: ИИ-симулятор диалога врача и пациента, речевые тренажёры с обратной связью, клинические речевые сценарии, жанровые задания и элементы формата AXIS. Результаты показали, что применение данных методов способствует развитию связной устной речи, повышению точности медицинских формулировок, формированию навыков эмпатичного объяснения и осознанного выбора речевых стратегий. Вместе с тем исследование носит пилотный характер и требует дальнейшей количественной верификации. Научная значимость работы состоит в рассмотрении культуры речи как интегративного компонента профессиональной подготовки будущего врача, а не как вспомогательного раздела языкового курса.

Ключевые слова: медико-биологический профиль, учебно-профессиональная коммуникация, медицинский русский язык, язык для специальных целей, проблемы обучения русскому языку.

Modern medical education can no longer be limited to the formation of only clinical knowledge and professional skills. Healthcare practice shows that the quality of medical care largely depends on how well the future doctor is able to clearly, ethically, logically and empathically build verbal interaction with the patient, colleagues and other participants in the treatment process. In this context, the culture of speech becomes not a secondary humanitarian component, but a part of the professional competence of a medical specialist [1].

This problem is particularly important when teaching Russian to medical students. For a future doctor, the Russian language acts not only as an academic discipline, but also as a tool for professional socialization: through it, the student learns medical terminology, models of clinical dialogue, norms for explaining the diagnosis, ways of asking questions, forms of speech tact and strategies for communicating with the patient. Therefore, teaching Russian at a medical university should be focused not on the isolated study of grammar and vocabulary, but on the development of professional speech culture [2].

International research in the field of medical communication emphasizes that the structure of communication between a doctor and a patient includes a number of mandatory communicative tasks: establishing contact, opening a conversation, collecting information, understanding the patient's position, transmitting information, agreeing on an action plan and completing a consultation. These elements were systematized in the Kalamazoo Consensus Statement, where medical communication is considered as a learnable and evaluated competence, rather than as an innate quality of a specialist. This approach is important for the methodology of teaching Russian to medical students, because it allows you to transfer work on speech from the general

plane of "speaking correctly" to a specific professional plane: "speaking clearly, evidently, ethically and appropriately in a medical situation" [3].

1. Aspegren, K. (1999). BEME Guide No.

2. Berkhof, M., van Rijssen, H. J., Schellart, A. J. M., Anema, J. R., & van der Beek, A. J. (2011). 152–162.

3. Lane, C., & Rollnick, S. (2007). The use of simulated patients and role-play in communication skills training: A review of the literature to August 2005. *Patient Education and Counseling*, 67(1–2), 13–20.

At the same time, there is a methodological gap in the actual practice of teaching Russian to medical students. On the one hand, there are developed models of teaching medical communication in the English-speaking and European traditions.

On the other hand, in Russian-language linguodidactics, a significant part of the work is focused on terminology, reading scientific texts and mastering the language of the specialty, while the culture of speech of the future doctor as a set of linguistic norms, professional ethics, empathy, genre literacy and communicative accuracy has not been studied systematically enough.

The question of how to combine teaching medical vocabulary, speech genres, dialogue with the patient and professional communication norms in the framework of the Russian language course is particularly poorly developed [4].

Thus, the relevance of the research is determined by the need to scientifically substantiate the role of speech culture in the professional training of medical students and to determine the methodological conditions for its formation in Russian language classes. The purpose of the article is to analyze scientific approaches to teaching medical communication and the Russian language to medical students, as well as to identify the possibilities of integrating speech culture into the professionally oriented language training of future doctors.

Literary review

Medical communication research forms the theoretical basis for understanding the doctor's speech culture as a professional competence. Makoul showed that a successful medical conversation is not random, but structured: the doctor must not only convey information, but also establish contact, understand the patient's point of view, agree on a treatment plan and correctly complete the interaction [5]. This approach is fundamental for teaching Russian: it allows you to build educational assignments around real communicative actions of a doctor, rather than around abstract grammatical topics. An important step in the development of this idea was the British consensus on the content of communicative training in medical education.

Von Fragstein et al., emphasize that teaching and evaluating clinical communication have become central components of the training of future doctors, and the program itself should be integrated into the educational process, rather than existing as a separate optional unit, which is especially important for Russian language courses at medical universities: the culture of speech should be formed not episodically, but

sequentially - through vocabulary, syntax, dialogic models, professional genres, and speech strategies [6].

4.Schouten, B. C., & Meeuwesen, L. (2006). Cultural differences in medical communication: A review of the literature. *Patient Education and Counseling*, 64(1-3), 21-34.

5.Makoul, G. (2001). Essential elements of communication in medical encounters: The Kalamazoo Consensus Statement. *Academic Medicine*, 76(4), 390-393.

6.Von Fragstein, M., Silverman, J., Cushing, A., Quilligan, S., Salisbury, H., & Wiskin, C. (2008). UK consensus statement on the content of communication curricula in undergraduate medical education. *Medical Education*, 42(11), 1100-1107.

A systematic review by Denniston et al., expands the understanding of communicative competence in medical education. The authors identified 205 learning outcomes grouped into four areas: knowledge, substantive skills, procedural skills, and perceptual skills, including the ability to recognize one's own ways of expressing emotions [7].

This is especially important for a linguist, because the culture of a doctor's speech is not limited to normality and includes the ability to choose the form of utterance, taking into account the addressee, the situation, the emotional state of the patient and the purpose of communication. However, this model needs linguistic and didactic adaptation: it presents communicative results well, but does not sufficiently reveal the linguistic mechanisms of their formation, such as working with intonation, speech clichés, interrogative constructions, explanatory models and label formulas.

A modern review by Venktaramana et al. shows that teaching communication skills in medical schools remains heterogeneous in structure, content, and assessment methods. The authors note that such programs are beneficial for doctors and patients, but require thoughtful design, phasing, institutional support and objective assessment. Such monitoring allows a critical assessment of the state of teaching Russian to medical students: the presence of separate dialogues, texts about diseases or lists of terms does not mean the full formation of speech culture [8]. A task system is needed in which the student gradually moves from understanding a professional text to creating his own oral and written statements in a medical situation.

In Russian-language linguodidactics, the problem of teaching medical students is more often considered through the category of "specialty language" [9]. Butorina, Guseva and Malakhova emphasize that the formation of professionally oriented communicative competence occurs in Russian language classes through work with medical and biological texts, special terminology, as well as through the development of oral and written speech. The advantage of this approach lies in its subject orientation: the student learns the language of the future profession not abstractly, but through professional material. However, the limitation of this approach lies in the fact that working with the term and scientific text does not always form a willingness to communicate with the patient live [10]. A doctor's medical speech includes not only the accuracy of a term, but also the ability to explain complex things in simple words, ask the correct question, mitigate disturbing information, and maintain an ethical

distance. Closer to the problem of speech culture is the study by Arzumanova and Bokizhanova, which examines the formation of clear and empathic medical communication skills among medical students in the framework of the course "Russian language and Speech Culture".

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7. Denniston, C., Molloy, E., Nestel, D., Woodward-Kron, R., & Keating, J. L. (2017).

8. Schouten, B. C., & Meeuwesen, L. (2006). Cultural differences in medical communication: A review of the literature. *Patient Education and Counseling*, 64(1–3), 21–34.

9. Makoul, G. (2001). Essential elements of communication in medical encounters: The Kalamazoo Consensus Statement. *Academic Medicine*, 76(4), 390–393.

10. Von Fragstein, M., Silverman, J., Cushing, A., Quilligan, S., Salisbury, H., & Wiskin, C. (2008). UK, 1100–1107.

The authors propose using artificial intelligence tools, virtual patients, and speech analysis systems to overcome the shortage of communicative practice in mass education, which combines a Russian-language speech culture course with a specific task of medical communication [11].

At the same time, this area requires caution: digital simulators can enhance the practical component of learning, but should not replace live pedagogical feedback, analysis of speech errors and work on semantic accuracy of utterance. Of particular importance is the genre approach to teaching Russian to medical students.

Dreyfeld shows that tasks for creative imitation of speech genres can be used in teaching RCT to students of a medical and biological profile: these can be infographics, posters, manuals, notes by a young doctor, medical blogs and other genres of educational and professional communication, since medical communication exists not only in the form of a doctor-patient dialogue, but also and in the form of written recommendations, preventive memos, explanatory materials and public educational texts [12]. They should include criteria for speech accuracy, logic, targeting, ethics, and genre relevance. The socio-cultural aspect of learning is revealed in the work of Nikitina et al., where cultural texts are considered as a means of forming linguistic, cultural and socio-cultural competence among students of a medical and biological profile, since the doctor's speech is always culturally conditioned: the ways of addressing, expressing sympathy, explaining the diagnosis and conducting a conversation depend on the norms of a particular linguistic community. The cultural text should be associated with the modeling of real situations of medical communication [13].

In general, an analysis of the literature shows that international studies describe the structure and goals of medical communication well, and Russian-language works reveal the specifics of teaching the language of the specialty, medical terminology, genre writing and socio-cultural competence. However, there is a scientific and methodological gap between these areas and a model has not been sufficiently developed that would consider the speech culture of medical students as an integrative result of teaching the Russian language, including normativity, terminological accuracy, clarity of explanation, genre competence, empathy and professional ethics. Therefore, a promising area of research is the development of a Russian language teaching methodology in which the future doctor's speech culture is formed through a system of professionally oriented tasks: analyzing medical texts, mastering

terminology, modeling a dialogue with a patient, transforming scientific information into an accessible explanation, creating genres of medical discourse and reflecting on speech behavior. This approach allows us to consider the Russian language not as an auxiliary discipline, but as a tool for professional training of a medical specialist.

11. Denniston, C., Molloy, E., Nestel, D., Woodward-Kron, R., & Keating, J. L. (2017).

12. Venktaramana, V., Loh, E. K. Y., Wong, C. J. W., et al. (2022). A systematic scoping review of communication skills training in medical schools between 2000 and 2020. *Medical Teacher*, 44(9), 997–1006.

13. Borowczyk, M., Stalmach-Przygoda, A., Doroszevska, A., et al. (2023). 23, 625.

Methodology

Several methods have been applied to improve the quality of teaching Russian as a foreign language among medical students, while taking into account their interests.

1. AI simulator of the doctor-patient dialogue One of the most modern approaches in which a student communicates not just with a teacher, but with a virtual patient: collects complaints, clarifies anamnesis, explains the diagnosis, and makes recommendations. This method is especially useful for medical students because it allows them to repeatedly train clinical dialogue in Russian.

2. Speech simulators with feedback You can use AI tools that analyze the student's response: how well he constructed the phrase, whether he used the term correctly, whether the speech sounds rude, whether there is a logic to the explanation. This is especially important for the culture of speech, because a medical student must speak not only correctly, but also clearly for the patient.

3. The method of clinical speech scenarios When using this method, the student works with real professional situations: collecting medical history; explaining the diagnosis; reporting unpleasant information; talking to an anxious patient; conversation with the patient's relatives; explanation of the treatment regimen; preventive conversation; recommendations after discharge.

4. Genre training of medical speech It is very modern to use not only dialogue, but also different genres of medical discourse. Students can create: a memo for the patient; a poster about disease prevention; a medical infographic; a brief recommendation after admission; a note from a young doctor; a medical blog; instructions for taking medication; a text for a social network about a healthy lifestyle.

5. The AXIS format is an objective structured clinical exam for the Russian language. The student receives a situation card and must complete a speech task in 3-5 minutes. For example:

- Task 1: Collect patient complaints.
- Task 2: explain the preparation for the blood test.
- Task 3: give recommendations after acute respiratory viral infections.
- Task 4: Calm an anxious patient.
- Task 5: Explain the side effects of the drug in simple terms.

Results

For three months, the above-mentioned methods of professionally oriented education were tested in Russian language classes with first-year medical students at the Tashkent International University of KIMYO. At the initial stage, it was revealed that the majority of first-year students had difficulty constructing a coherent oral statement on a medical topic. Students' speech was often fragmentary: students knew individual words and terms, but found it difficult to use them in dialogue. The use of the AI simulator of the doctor-patient dialogue allowed to expand the scope of students' speech practice. The virtual patient was used to simulate simple clinical situations: complaints of headache, fever, abdominal pain, weakness, cough, increased blood pressure.

The students learned to ask questions in stages: first, they clarified the main complaint, then the duration of the symptom, the nature of the pain, the accompanying signs and the general condition of the patient. As a result, by the end of the third month, students began to build a dialogue more confidently, used full question constructions more often, and began to follow the logical sequence of the medical conversation. Speech simulators with feedback were used to analyze the students' oral and written responses. Special attention was paid to grammatical correctness, the accuracy of terms, the logic of explanation and speech ethics. Students edited their own phrases, replacing rude or overly complex formulations with more understandable and correct ones. For example, the phrase "You have a bad analysis" was replaced by "There are changes in the analysis, so you need to undergo an additional examination." The phrase "You should take pills" was transformed into a more professional form: "You are recommended to take the drug according to the prescribed regimen." This type of work contributed to the development of speech self-correction skills.

The method of clinical speech scenarios has shown high efficiency in the formation of professional and communicative skills. During the trial period of the method, students worked with situations of collecting medical history, explaining the diagnosis in simple words, communicating with an anxious patient, talking with the patient's relatives, explaining the treatment regimen and recommendations after discharge.

The most productive tasks turned out to be where the student had to not just reproduce a ready-made dialogue, but choose a speech strategy on his own. For example, in the situation of "an anxious patient before a blood test," students learned to use soothing phrases: "Don't worry, this procedure takes a few minutes," "I'll explain to you how to prepare," "If you feel unwell, tell the medical professional right away."

Genre training of medical speech allowed students to develop written professional speech. During the classes, students created memos for the patient, brief recommendations after the appointment, instructions for preparing for tests, preventive posters and simple medical infographics.

At the final stage, the adapted AXIS format was used to evaluate speech skills in Russian. Students received situation cards and completed a specific communicative task within 3-5 minutes: collect patient complaints, explain preparations for a blood test, make recommendations after acute respiratory viral infections, calm an anxious patient, and explain possible side effects of medication in simple language. Based on the results of the observation, it was found that students began to better follow the

response structure: greeting, clarifying the problem, explaining, recommending, and ending the conversation.

In general, the three-month testing showed that the use of these methods contributes to the transition from passive assimilation of medical vocabulary to the active formation of professional and speech competence. First-year students have improved their verbal confidence, expanded their active vocabulary on medical topics, and improved their ability to ask clarifying questions, explain information in simple words, and use ethically correct speech formulas. A particularly important result was that students began to realize the difference between "knowing a term" and "being able to explain it to a patient."

Discussion

The approbation of the proposed model shows that the speech culture of medical students is formed more effectively when language learning goes beyond normative correctness and is included in the context of professional action. In this case, the Russian language acts not only as a means of transmitting information, but also as a tool for clinical thinking: the student learns not just to name a symptom or diagnosis, but to build the speech logic of medical communication. This fundamentally distinguishes professionally oriented learning from the traditional approach, where terminology is often studied in isolation from the communication situation. At the same time, it should be critically noted that the positive dynamics could be related not only to the chosen methods, but also to the overall intensity of speech practice. Therefore, further studies should include a control group, diagnostic scales before and after training, as well as an expert assessment of oral speech. Without these procedures, the conclusions remain promising, but preliminary.

Conclusion

The results of the introduction of modern teaching methods have shown that the Russian language course for medical students can perform not only a linguistic, but also a professional and communicative function. The use of AI simulators, speech simulators, clinical scenarios, genre tasks and the AXIS format allows future doctors to form a culture of speech as an important component of professional training. The results obtained confirm the need for further development of a practice-oriented model of teaching Russian at a medical university, where the focus is not on mechanical memorization of terms, but on the ability to clearly, ethically and professionally interact with the patient.

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